

The EN-TRACK project: Energy Efficiency Performance-Tracking Platform for Benchmarking Savings and Investments in Buildings

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Abstract. Buildings are responsible for 40% of the energy consumption in Europe, and 75% of the building stock is energy inefficient. Renovation of buildings for improved energy efficiency is a key priority in the European climate strategy and requires increased investments by the private sector. One of the principal challenges to this is the lack of statistical data on the actual energy and costs savings achieved with them. The required energy and investment data is still hard to access because it is decentralized and in different formats and only a small part of this can be used to produce reliable empirical evidence on the performance of the energy efficiency investments.

The EN-TRACK project meets the challenge by developing an open-source big data platform enabling massive data gathering, making the data comparable and interoperable with other existing databases, analysing this data and offering relevant results to key stakeholders. This supports better (more informed, more transparent and faster) decision-making, contributes to the de-risking of energy efficiency investments in buildings and facilitates process of closing investment deals. The platform has been put into practice in two large demonstrators in Catalonia and Bulgaria and has collected energy and investment data from more than 5000 buildings and 3000 energy efficiency measures, offering building performance monitoring, savings evaluation, and benchmarking of investments' performance.

The presentation will make an overview of the EN-TRACK's approach to data gathering, harmonisation, and benchmarking, and will outline its exploitation potential for increasing the energy efficiency investments in buildings.

Keywords: Energy efficiency investment, big data, building performance monitoring.